

Research Article

Protecting Against Cyber Threats: Strategies & Best Practices for Effective Cyber Security

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Abstract: *This research article is titled Protecting against cyber threats: strategies & best practices for effective cyber security. This topic was chosen to be studied because the writer is aware that many people do not care about cybercrime and cyber security which is becoming more and more worrying today. The objective of the study in this research article is to examine the level of public awareness, especially those involved in the business field, of cybercrime and cyber security. In addition, the research of this article also aims to identify what types of cybercrime often occur as well as the correct steps or strategies to prevent yourself and your company from becoming a victim of cybercrime. This research method is implemented by searching for several reference articles in online databases such as Emerald Insight, EzAccess, Science Direct and also Google search engine. A literature review is a survey of academic books, journals, and other materials pertinent to a specific problem, field of study, or theory, and it offers a description, synopsis, and critical assessment of these works. The purpose of literature reviews is to show readers how your research fits into the greater body of knowledge and to give an overview of the sources you used to investigate a particular topic. This research article discusses the true meaning of cybercrime from the point of view of research analysts, as well as systematic ways to prevent this cybercrime from occurring. This writing is more directed to business practitioners which companies or industries will be more at risk of experiencing cybercrime cases. Today, hackers or criminals are smarter and more forward-thinking in their tactics to steal customer's personal data and make money with each stolen data. Furthermore, the type of cybercrime not only involves large industries, but ordinary Internet users are also likely to become victims of cybercrime. As a result, this research paper has a positive impact because it contains research findings that cover all aspects of cyber security and cybercrime.*

Keywords: *Cyber security; cybercrime; business; Internet; aware.*

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1. INTRODUCTION

In today's digitally-driven world, cybersecurity is a critical concern for individuals and organizations alike and has become a critical aspect of our lives. Cyber threats come in many forms, from phishing scams and malware attacks to ransomware and data breaches. The consequences of a successful cyber attack can be devastating, ranging from financial losses and reputational damage to legal liabilities and compromised personal information. It is essential to have strategies and best practices in place to protect against cyber threats effectively. This essay will also explore some of the

most effective cyber security strategies and best practices, providing insights into how individuals and organizations can minimize their risks and better protect themselves against cyber threats.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This study uses the manner of a literature review. This type of research method is used to ensure the writer can complete this research article carefully because the previous study is used as a reference. The author uses scientific materials such as articles and information from relevant websites. All these materials are obtained from online database and Internet platforms such as Emerald Insight, EzAccess, Science Direct and Google search engine. The author used a total of 4 materials including articles and websites that are closely related to the topic studied by the author. This allows researchers to make comparisons and use these materials as a reference to complete their studies. Furthermore, this online content article and webpage has important content related to cyber security and cybercrime which gives researchers the opportunity to complete this study more easily and provide comprehensive understanding to researchers.

3.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

No matter what the discipline, the foundation of all academic research activity is developing research and connecting it to existing knowledge. Therefore, getting it right is crucial for all academics. This is the reason that using a literature review as a research approach is more pertinent than using earlier studies. This evaluation of the literature can be seen of as a more or less organised method of compiling and combining earlier studies (Baumeister and Leary, 1997; Tranfield, Denyer, and Smart, 2003). According to Webster and Watson (2002), studies and research techniques that are well-executed and efficient lay a strong foundation for knowledge advancement and the facilitation of theory building. A literature review will be used to address the research topic since it combines empirical data and viewpoints from numerous sources. The claim made by Tranfield et al. (2003) that a literature review is the best method for combining study results to demonstrate evidence at a meta level and tries to uncover Areas where more research is required is used to support this argument. This is important for developing the conceptual model and creating the theoretical framework. The conventional method of describing the literature is also less detailed and won't be applied consistently (Tranfield et al., 2003).

As researchers, we have conducted a literature review to help us better understand and add knowledge to this study. Cybercrime, according to Norton Security Symantec Corporation, is any crime that involves computers or the internet in some way (Norton, 2016). Deshmukh and Chaudary (2014) stated that the phenomenal growth in the use of trained people also increased the global spam rate, malware rate and phishing rate rapidly, bank account fraud as a cybercrime also increased at a higher rate. This is supported by Wavefront (2016) when the first account of cybercrime occurred in 1970 involving a teller at the New York Dime Savings Bank who used a computer to embezzle over \$2 million in money. Julien (2016) also stated that the first spam email was sent through ARPAnet, the United States Department of Defense Network by a Digital Equipment Corporation marketing executive after 8 years had passed. Since the usage of computers has grown quickly over time, cybercrime has dramatically expanded. Threats from cybercrime to computer security can take many different forms, from quick attacks to extensive criminal activity.

Cybercrime has many incentives for hackers. A hacker is usually defined as a person who uses a computer "to gain unauthorized access to data" (Oxford Dictionary, 2018). According to Smith et al. (2011), cybercriminals are motivated by economic, personal, ideological, and structural factors. Hackers might see a chance to further their own interests or carry out personal revenge. Selling information that has been taken on the black market is another way that cybercriminals can benefit. Governments have

engaged in cybercrime on a global scale. Cybercriminals frequently pick their victims carefully and scan the target for weak points. The eight cybercrimes listed above have one thing in common: most of the time, the victim must take part in some way for the crime to happen and to be effective. The victim is exposed to such attacks because they either comply with the request, engage with the perpetrator, or lack proper defences like anti-virus or anti-intrusion software. The importance of human behavioural aspects in preventing cybercrime is acknowledged in the literature (Hadlington and Chivers, 2018).

Conclusions made by Sarre et al. (2018) that the aspect of education is one of the best responses to cybercrime, especially education that provides exposure about victimization to them. This is supported by Cornish and Clarke (2003) because it is argued in their study a further understanding of crime prevention approaches that focus on self-protection by potential victims and help reduce the chances of crime that will occur. Sherizen (1991) states that there is an important socio-technical approach to the problem of computer crime. It needs to determine where the social and psychological line is drawn between normal and deviant and split into two poles of groups between them that cause mutual misunderstandings and perform unethical tasks. To build crime prevention activities based on evidence, effective and efficient actions in countering these cybercrime activities, it is necessary to understand the numerous hazards of online victimisation and crime prevention in the online context. Grabosky, 2001; Renys, 2010; Drew and Farrell, 2018).

4.0 FINDINGS

The findings of the study show that several reference articles use different content where each researcher has a different view on the definition of cybercrime, types of cybercrime and how to protect against cybercrime. Explanations related to other study findings are discussed in the paragraphs below.

4.1 Definition of cybercrime

Cybercrime is the term used to describe illicit behaviours carried out using digital technology or the Internet, according to the paper "The Effect of Cybercrime on Open Innovation Policies in Technology Firms." Data theft, hacking, identity theft, and the dissemination of malware or viruses are a few examples of these actions. Cybercrime can have major negative consequences for both persons and companies, including financial loss, harm to one's reputation, and disruptions of essential infrastructure and services. In order to defend themselves from cyber dangers, it is crucial for both individuals and businesses to employ appropriate cybersecurity measures. (Raten, 2019).

According to the article "A study of cybercrime victimisation and prevention: exploring the use of online crime prevention behaviours and strategies", cybercrime is any criminal action that is carried out through the internet or other digital communication technology (Jacqueline, 2019). This covers a wide range of unlawful actions, including cyberstalking, online fraud, identity theft, and hacking, among others. In the current digital era, cybercrime is a severe threat to everyone, including people, corporations, and governments.

Cybercrime is any criminal conduct involving the use of computers, networks, or the internet, according to the article "Examination of Cybercrime and its Effects on Corporate Stock Value". Cybercriminals may infiltrate computer systems to inflict harm or disruption, or they may steal sensitive information such as trade secrets, financial data, or personal information. The financial performance and reputation of businesses, as well as the people who are victims, can be significantly impacted by cybercrime (Smith, Johnson, Jones & Lawrence, 2018).

Cybercrime is defined as criminal activity carried out utilising digital technology including computers, smartphones, and the internet, according to the paper "Awareness towards cybercrime among secondary school students: the role of gender and school management." These actions could

include, among others, online harassment, phishing, hacking, and identity theft. The essay also emphasises how critical it is to educate people about cybercrime, especially secondary school children, in order to safeguard them from harm and provide them the tools they need to make wise decisions online (Mudit Kumar Verma & Shyam Sundar Kushwaha, 2020).

4.2 Types of cybercrime

There are numerous forms of cybercrime that the general public may be aware of. Website fraud is one of the cybercrimes that are prevalent today and are frequently reported. Spoof is interchangeable with the words deceive, hoax, and trick. Website spoofing is the practise of creating a website that imitates another one in order to deceive users into thinking it is the real deal. This criminal behaviour is carried out to propagate harmful and malicious software, get access to user computers, steal data, or steal money. This dishonest practise is copying authentic websites and exploiting corporate branding, user faces, domain names, and corporate style to deceive people into entering usernames and passwords in a website without any scepticism or hesitation. This gives dishonest people a way to steal the data of every user, use it for nefarious purposes, and install malicious software on users' machines.

Ransomware is another typical form of cybercrime. Modern cybercrime known as ransomware occurs when hackers steal important data and demand a hefty ransom in return. It is sometimes referred to as the long-standing crime of extortion. This crime generally involves the encryption of a company's data and happens in the majority of enterprises. If this ransomware crime takes place, a company's business will be restricted or abruptly stopped, which will have several negative impacts including preventing people from performing their tasks and costing them their livelihood. In this case, without recoverable backup data, the business companies involved are generally at the mercy of attackers or criminals who will hold high-value data as hostages in exchange for currency and so on. Ransomware is becoming a criminal activity and should be a major concern in all organizations whether in the business industry or any type of industry. Based on recent research, ransomware breaches have increased by 13% over the past five years combined. For instance, are people more likely to use virus protection but less likely to utilise other cybercrime preventative measures if they have personally encountered a specific type of cybercrime, such as ransomware? Social media privacy settings that are relevant to their earlier victimisation should be kept in tact. What impact does the diversity of reported cybercrimes have on the application of crime prevention techniques? 2020 (Jacqueline).

The last type of cybercrime is IOT hacking. It is common knowledge that the Internet of Things is a brand-new era that bravely offers insights into the daily activities and commercial activities conducted by users online. All devices that have access to the Internet are gathering and exchanging data with one another whether the user allows this update or not. Data is valuable in this context, thus hackers and other cybercriminals would try to take advantage of any equipment that gathers it. If more users link objects to the Internet, hackers and other cybercriminals will have better opportunities and rewards. Thus, it's crucial that every user adopt security measures by enforcing passwords, whether they're for personal or professional use. Due to carelessness in failing to make the password more secure and other connected issues, it frequently happens that the user will lose all the crucial data kept on the device.

4.3 Strategies and best practices for cybercrime

One strategy for situational crime prevention that focuses on lowering the possibility of these crimes occurring is self-defence. Because the fast growth and progress of technology have opened various fields, new opportunities, and efficient resources for organisations of all sizes, we frequently hear that cybercrime may occur at any time and from any location, regardless of rank, age, or gender. Furthermore, the presence of the internet aided in the development of this technology. The truth is that the internet is a vital asset for the country, and national security is dependent on it. Self-defence, on the other hand, is one of the wisest techniques for avoiding being a victim of this crime. One of the best ways to protect oneself from this crime is to be cautious when using public Wi-Fi. We already know that internet users are extremely glad and delighted if wi-fi is available everywhere for the convenience of using the internet, but consumers are frequently dissatisfied because public wi-fi is one of the chances for thieves to steal our personal data without our knowledge or consent. Users should also encrypt and recover essential data. This is because hackers can carry out illegal objectives by copying vital information if users encrypt data stored on smartphones and laptops. The answer is to save as a copy and keep locally on an external hard drive that is only intermittently connected to a computer, such as in a cloud storage system, if the data is vital, such as medical information, or irreplaceable, such as family photographs.

According to Leukfelft (2014) and Miethe and Meier (1994), this is important to investigate the function of self-protection in reducing the harm of victimization because it provides an alternative that may be more effective to reduce the incidence of cybercrime. Among the strategies that are so effective in reducing the crime rate is to focus on these 25 strategies, Cornish and Clarke's situational crime prevention model can be used to fight this crime. Among the main tactics is to "increase efforts" surrounding crime. The strategy is to harden targets, control access to facilities, handicap offenders and controls/weapons. While to "reduce the reward" for committing this crime is to extend care, help natural supervision, reduce anonymity, use place managers and strengthen formal supervision. This risk-increasing strategy opens up opportunities for criminals to continue committing crimes. Then, this "diminishing reward" can hide targets, remove targets, identify assets, disrupt markets and deny benefits. The themes of "reducing provocation" and "eliminating excuses" can lessen anger and stress, prevent arguments, lessen lust and temptation, fend off peer pressure, and discourage imitation. In order to reduce target conformance in a number of classics like aggressive and sexual sorts, 25 strategies have previously been recognised in earlier work as one of the most effective approaches.

Furthermore, this cybercrime is one of the ones that is also at the top of the list. The authorities should collaborate with other federal departments and organisations, such as the Department of Homeland Security, to address this criminal issue. Aside from the Criminal Complaints Centre, the public is also informed of the presence of a number of procedures designed to make it easier for individuals to report any suspicious conduct to authorities. This is because the authorities are organisations that are extremely dedicated to combating cybercrime. Next, improving security, including employing personal data prevention methods to secure electronic devices such as user computers in terms of identification and transaction protection, is how to protect against cybercrime. One method is to always install or update antivirus and antispyware software and to be wary of downloaded files and fraudulent email attachments. To secure the firm's personal data, each company must have the best backup plan to protect the company's name by having a strategy to manage publicity and prepare comments for the media, and they must also be prepared to spend large sums of money during the repair and recovery phases. The corporation must, among other things, adopt strategic steps to protect the interests of the business and its many stakeholders, such as the owners of each share,

customers, and the general public. Furthermore, if a firm encounters or is involved in cybercrime, it will have an influence through rumours that intend to tarnish the company's name.

Next, a wise user can avoid becoming a victim of the situation by participating in some way, i.e., either asking for something from the offender during a conversation or by being vulnerable to attacks and harassment due to a lack of protection, such as anti-virus or anti-intrusion software. If a victim does not react to a phishing email, for example, the fraudster cannot access their personal information. The virus cannot be installed on the victim's machine if they do not click on the offered link. Given this, it is important to comprehend the role of victims in cybercrime and, in particular, to look into the role of victims as a crucial component of stopping and preventing cybercrime.

5. DISCUSSION

The study carried out covers the awareness that needs to be taken into consideration regarding cyber security and cybercrime. This paper discusses what cybercrime is, the type of cybercrime that always occurs in today's society and also how to take good steps or strategies to prevent the occurrence of cybercrime that is becoming increasingly worrying today. Based on the findings, it can be known that a large number of people do not know about the dangers of cybercrime which is becoming more prevalent today. Studies conducted in business organizations show that they carry out open innovative activities which provide space and opportunity for cybercriminals to steal data or hack the organization's website easily. This is a concern for researchers because perhaps more business organizations will experience high losses due to uncontrollable internal technical problems. As a result, there is an urgent need to develop new strategies to combat cybercrime and shift much more towards a crime prevention approach that focuses on preventing victimisation from happening (Webster and Drew, 2017).

In addition, as expected when so many objects are connected to the Internet, the number of cybercrime cases increases. This is said because, the majority of society today depends on the Internet and every activity carried out will be related to the Internet. Therefore, every personal data stored will be easily stolen by cybercriminals for their immoral purposes. Previous studies have also shown that there is still a lack of awareness among the world community to be more careful in the use of the Internet and do not care to be more alert with something that causes doubts or misgivings. Cyber Crime is a serious crime, it breaches someone's privacy and confidential data and also exposes to financial losses. It involves infringement of human rights as well as of governmental laws. Therefore, one must consistently follow all the precautions discussed earlier, because 'Prevention is better than cure', as the well-known saying states" (Sonika Bharati, 2019).

6. CONCLUSION

As a result, cybercrime is a widespread problem that all users encounter, regardless of age or gender, demonstrating that men and women are equally vulnerable to being targeted and becoming victims of this criminal issue. Furthermore, this crime occurs without our knowledge in every act we perform. Through four publications that are closely relevant to the author's field of study. Furthermore, we can observe from this study that each publication has distinct study outcomes owing to the diverse scope of the investigation. The breadth of each author's research implies that each author investigates the same issue but in a different way. Following that, various writers generate a diversity of thoughts and discoveries that are intriguing despite their diverse backgrounds and writing styles. This is because the variety of these concepts might generate highly fascinating ideas for the researcher to gather information. Not only that, but the time of study causes each of these articles to have their own unique features because it is possible that the author studied this topic at a different time because each of these articles does not have the same continuity. For example, the author of this article studies in a year that

is not serious and worrying, which will result in a finding as an issue of this crime can still be saved, whereas the author who studies in a year of such increased cases will not.

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